

COMPARING REST API AND KAFKA IN THE CONTEXT OF FINANCIAL APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

This paper explores the comparison between two data transmission technologies – REST API and Kafka used in financial applications. The study examines architectural differences, performance, reliability, and applicability of each technology in various scenarios such as banking transactions, external system integration, and stream analytics. Particular attention is given to the capabilities and limitations of REST API in synchronous data processing and the strengths of Kafka in stream analytics and handling large volumes of real-time data. The paper also discusses the potential for hybrid solutions combining both technologies to create more universal and scalable financial platforms.

Keywords: REST API, Kafka, financial applications, stream analytics, integration, scalability.

Introduction

Modern financial systems are complex technological ecosystems that are actively evolving in response to the growth of digitalization and the increasing need for fast and reliable ways of processing data. They are based on data transfer mechanisms, such as API, which provide communication between different systems and participants in the financial sector. On the other hand, streaming platforms are becoming an important tool for working with huge amounts of data in real time, especially for analytics and monitoring purposes.

In banking applications, including letter of credit systems, the role of data transfer technologies is extremely important. Both the speed and reliability of transactions and their compliance with security requirements depend on them. Among the available solutions, REST API remains a classic approach to building interactions, while Kafka is an example of modern event-oriented platforms.

The objective of this study is to compare two technologies – REST API and Kafka in terms of their archi-

ture, performance, reliability and applicability in financial applications. Based on the analysis, scenarios will be identified in which the use of one technology is preferable to the other. This will allow for a deeper understanding of their roles in banking systems and identify ways to effectively integrate them into the future development of financial platforms.

Main part. Theoretical foundations and architectural differences

REST API and Kafka represent two fundamentally different approaches to data transfer and interaction in information systems. These technologies are widely used in financial applications, but their architectural foundations differ significantly, defining the areas of optimal application.

REST API (Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface) is a standard for organizing interaction between a client and a server based on the request-response principle. It is based on the HTTP protocol, which makes the REST API universal and compatible with most modern web applications (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. REST API architecture [1]

One of the main advantages of REST API is the ease of its integration with existing systems, which makes it a popular choice for developing interfaces in banking applications. The use of REST API is strictly regulated by security standards such as OAuth (Open Authorization) and JWT (JSON Web Token), which ensure data protection from unauthorized access. However, REST API has certain limitations. It is best suited for synchronous operations, but has difficulties when

dealing with large volumes of data or high load, especially in scenarios that require real-time processing.

Kafka, unlike the REST API, follows an event-oriented architecture and is designed for asynchronous data transfer. This technology operates on the basis of a publish-subscribe model, where messages are written to data brokers and distributed among subscribers (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Kafka architecture [2]

This model allows Kafka to provide high throughput and fault tolerance. Financial applications, such as transaction monitoring systems and anti-fraud platforms, actively use Kafka to process data streams in real time. For example, in anti-fraud solutions, Kafka allows processing hundreds of thousands of events per second, identifying suspicious transactions. Its architecture includes data replication mechanisms, which increase system reliability and minimize information loss even in the event of node failures.

One of the important aspects of Kafka is its support for horizontal scaling, making it an ideal choice for applications that require working with ever-growing volumes of data. For example, large banks use Kafka to combine data from various sources – branches, online platforms, and mobile applications – into a single streaming system for analytics. However, using Kafka requires complex infrastructure and significant initial costs, which can be a limitation for smaller organizations [3].

Thus, the REST API and Kafka represent two different approaches to organizing data transfer: the REST API with its synchronous nature and simplicity is suitable for standard requests and operations, while Kafka with its asynchronous architecture and scalability is aimed at stream processing and complex analytical tasks.

Comparative analysis of architectural approaches

Comparison of the architectural approaches of REST API and Kafka demonstrates fundamental differences in their interaction models, scalability, reliability and scope of application, which makes these technologies suitable for different scenarios in financial applications. Each of these approaches has its own strengths and weaknesses, determining its choice depending on the requirements of a particular task.

Interaction model is the main difference between REST API and Kafka. REST API uses a synchronous approach based on client requests and immediate server

response. This method ensures strict sequencing of operations, which is especially important in transactional systems where guaranteed delivery and execution of requests in real time is required. For example, in the processing of letters of credit, REST API allows for strict control over the sequence of steps: document verification, transaction confirmation, and payment execution. However, this approach is limited in scale due to its dependence on the state of the server, which must be available to process each request [4].

Kafka, on the other hand, is built on an asynchronous architecture using a publish-subscribe model. This provides independence between producers that create events and consumers that process them. This separation allows Kafka to support high throughput and process millions of messages per second, making it suitable for streaming analytics tasks. For example, a financial transaction monitoring system can collect real-time transaction data from various platforms and analyze it using Kafka, which is almost impossible for a REST API due to its limited scalability [5].

Reliability and fault tolerance are critical features for financial applications. REST API relies on the reliability of servers and network infrastructure, which makes it vulnerable to failures. If the REST API server becomes unavailable, operations cannot be completed, which is critical in high-stakes banking systems. On the other hand, Kafka integrates replication mechanisms that ensure data integrity even if individual nodes fail. In the event of a failure of one of the brokers, the system automatically switches to replicated data, minimizing the risk of information loss. This property makes Kafka preferable for systems such as anti-fraud solutions, where data loss can lead to serious consequences [6].

Scalability also plays a significant role in choosing the right technology. REST API scales mainly vertically, which requires increasing the computing power of servers. This method is suitable for systems with a static and predictable load, but is not suitable when one would need to process much larger volumes of simul-

taneous requests. However, Kafka has horizontal scaling support, i.e., you can increase the number of nodes in the cluster to increase performance. This approach is very handy for banks processing much volumes of data, e.g., when they are required to process streams of transactions from various branches and online channels.

Application of technologies in specific scenarios also demonstrates their unique advantages. REST API is ideal for transactional systems where the synchronicity of operations and deterministic execution of requests are critical. For example, letter of credit management systems that require a strict sequence of actions and instant confirmation of status cannot operate effectively based on asynchronous solutions. At the same time, Kafka finds its application in scenarios where there is a need to process large data in real time, such as streaming analytics or data integration with machine learning solutions in order to support predictive analytics. For instance, it is used in banks to detect anomalies in transactions, where data are collected and processed

simultaneously without waiting for the operations to be finalized.

Thus, the REST API and Kafka reflect two different approaches to data transfer architecture, each with its own strengths. The REST API provides simplified development and synchronous operations, making it ideal for transactional systems. Kafka, with its asynchronous model, high scalability and reliability, is suitable for working with large data streams and tasks requiring operational analytics. These differences highlight the need for careful selection of technology depending on the requirements of the financial application.

Analysis of applicability in financial applications

Financial applications place high demands on the performance, reliability, and flexibility of data transfer technologies [7]. REST API and Kafka demonstrate their applicability in various scenarios based on the specifics of operations, the volume of data, and the nature of system interactions (table 1).

Table 1

Evaluation of REST API and Kafka for various tasks in financial applications

Task	REST API	Kafka
Payment processing	Suitable for synchronous transactions.	Not suitable for immediate responses.
Integration with external API	Ideal for standard interfaces.	Suitable, but less commonly used.
Data aggregation	Limited for large data volumes.	Excellent for stream analytics.
Fraud detection	Can be used for basic checks.	Ideal for real-time analysis.
Data security	Uses standard security protocols (OAuth, JWT).	Requires additional effort for security.
Loan application processing	Suitable for synchronous processing.	Not suitable for synchronous transactions.
Responding to market changes	Not suitable for real time.	Ideal for real-time data processing.
Transaction and operation processing	Suitable for low-volume transactions.	Ideal for high-load systems.

REST API is often used to implement traditional banking functions that require synchronous interaction. In letter of credit management systems, the REST API ensures a strict sequence of operations, such as document verification, confirmation of terms, and transaction completion. These systems rely on guaranteed determinism of processes, where each customer request must be processed immediately with the provision of the transaction status. REST API is used for integration between banks and third-party providers, allowing customers to manage their finances from a single application. However, REST API is less effective for high data volumes or complex analytical tasks that require a constant flow of information.

Kafka, on the contrary, is widely used in tasks where it is necessary to process data in real time, while ensuring high throughput and resilience to failures. One of the striking examples is the use of Kafka in anti-fraud systems. Such systems analyze large streams of transaction data in real time, identifying suspicious transactions based on established patterns. Thanks to the Kafka architecture, event processing occurs in parallel, which allows scaling the system and ensuring prompt threat detection. In addition, Kafka is actively used to monitor financial transactions in real time.

Banking platforms integrate it to aggregate transaction data coming from various channels, including online banking, mobile applications, and branches.

Another area of application for Kafka is big data analytics. In banks with a large volume of clients, Kafka allows collecting and analyzing data on transactions, user behavior, and other metrics that are used to make management decisions [8]. For example, financial institutions can use Kafka to analyze customer transactions to identify trends, predict demand for services, or personalize offers. These scenarios require a high-performance system capable of processing millions of events per second, which is not possible using the REST API.

When choosing a technology for a particular application, it is important to consider the nature of the interactions. REST API is ideal for tasks with a synchronous transaction model, such as traditional banking transactions, letter of credit systems, and integration with external partners. Kafka, on the other hand, is optimal for streaming analytics, transaction monitoring, and tasks that require high scalability. For example, a bank looking to integrate streaming analytics into its infrastructure to improve risk management would make a better choice for Kafka.

Thus, the applicability of REST API and Kafka in financial applications is determined by the specifics of the tasks. REST API is better suited for synchronous processing that involves high-precision handling of requests and strict orderings. Kafka, since it's scalable and handles data in real-time, is best suited with streaming data processing and analytics-based systems with enhanced complexity. These technologies, although different in nature, successfully complement each other, creating the basis for modern financial solutions.

Conclusion

A comparative analysis of REST API and Kafka shows that each of these technologies has its own area of application in financial applications. REST API is ideal for synchronous operations that require a strict sequence of actions, such as banking transactions and letter of credit systems. This technology provides ease of integration and a high degree of compatibility with external systems, which makes it a preferred choice for traditional financial operations. However, its limitations in processing large volumes of data and scalability make it less effective for tasks related to streaming analytics or real-time.

Kafka, with its asynchronous architecture and high scalability, is more suitable for working with large data flows, such as transaction monitoring or anti-fraud systems. It provides resilience to failures and allows for efficient data processing in real time. In the future, it is possible to develop hybrid solutions that use the strengths of both technologies to build more versatile and powerful financial platforms.

References

1. REST API Developer Guide / Salesforce // URL: https://resources.docs.salesforce.com/latest/latest/en-us/sfdc/pdf/api_rest.pdf (date of application: 12.04.2025).

2. Apache Kafka Overview / Cloudera // URL: <https://docs.cloudera.com/runtime/7.2.16/kafka-overview/kafka-overview.pdf> (date of application: 12.04.2025).

3. Sidorov D. A comparative analysis of component-based architectures in web design for scalable applications // Cold Science. 2024. №. 8. P. 24-31. EDN: BROOLR

4. Gowda P. Best Practices in REST API Design for Enhanced Scalability and Security. // Journal of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Data Science. 2024. №. 2(1). P. 827-830. DOI: 10.51219/jaimld/priyanka-gowda/202 EDN: MPNSFA

5. Sethi S. Design and Optimization of a Zookeeper and Kafka-Based Messaging Broker for Asynchronous Processing in High Availability and Low Latency Applications. // J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res. 2024. №. 3(2). P. 01-07. DOI: 10.33140/JCTCSR.03.02.02

6. Yadav P. Advanced Authentication and Authorization Mechanisms in Apache Kafka: Enhancing Security for High-Volume Data Processing Environments. // Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences Technology. 2024. №. 6(8). P. 2-6. DOI: 10.47363/JEAST/2024(6)E110

7. Balgimbayev A. Development of innovative interfaces to enhance user experience in digital banking products // International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science. 2024. Vol. 6. №. 12. P. 2348-2353.

8. Alam M. Real-Time Analytics In Streaming Big Data: Techniques And Applications. // Journal of Science and Engineering Research. 2024. №. 1(01). P. 104-122.